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Improving Reproductive Health Understanding for Ethnic Minority Women and Girls in Viet Nam

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Abstract:

This paper uses qualitative research methods, namely in-depth interviews and group interviews, to determine the state of knowledge and understanding of the reproductive health of ethnic minority women and girls in Viet Nam. The sample included 852 subjects who classified demographics by age from 15 to 49, ethnicity, education status and number of pregnancies. The interview revolves around reproductive health issues. Specifically, 6 topics were explored: knowledge of reproductive health care, access to information on reproductive health, views on premarital sex and contraception, views on unwanted pregnancies, abortion and sexually transmitted diseases, knowledge of family planning, knowledge of pre- and postpartum health care. Although the situation of reproductive health in ethnic minority communities in general has improved over the years, maternal mortality rates, rates of infection with sexually transmitted diseases and unsafe abortions remain high in many ethnic minority communities. An important reason for this situation is that knowledge of reproductive health care is still not adequate and easily accessible in these areas. The results of the study are used to recommend useful measures and recommendations to improve the understanding of reproductive health for ethnic minority women and girls in Viet Nam

Keywords: reproductive health, women and girls, ethnic minorities

1. Introduction

Reproductive health is already an important part of general health and a central feature of human development. A society where women do not have healthy reproductive health will lead to high maternal mortality and morbidity. This is a concern in developing countries (M. Haque, 2015). In the past few years, reproductive health and rights issues have been increasingly seen as social issues that need attention throughout developed and developing countries. Viet Nam has made significant progress in important aspects of family health and wellbeing. However, ethnic minority women and girls are still facing a lot of problems related to reproductive health.

Viet Nam has made significant progress in improving people's SRH over the past decades, becoming one of only 9 countries in the world to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDG) maternal mortality reduction target by 2015. However, inequalities related to SRH rights and care persist. Although the maternal mortality rate has decreased from 233 cases per 100,000 live births in 1990 to 46 cases per 100,000 live births in 2019, the rate among ethnic minorities is 2-3 times higher. The proportion of pregnant ethnic minority women who go to health facilities for antenatal examinations as well as give birth at health facilities only reaches 86.4%. On the other hand, the rate of child marriage in ethnic minorities has decreased over the years but remains high (21.9% in 2019) and focuses on many compatriots such as Mong 51.5%, Array 47.2%, Xinh Mun 44.8%, Plating 39.2%. Early marriage, pregnancy and childbirth in adolescence, when the mother's body is not fully developed, ignorant, experienced and psychologically ready to become pregnant and give birth greatly affects maternal health, the normal development of the fetus and newborn (Ngo Thi Van Phong, 2019). This is responsible for the increase in the rate of malnutrition of ethnic minority children, the increase in mortality among ethnic minority children under 1 year old and under 5 years old, the increase in maternal mortality of ethnic minorities related to maternity (World Bank and National Institute of Nutrition, 2019).

Health knowledge is considered one of the important factors that help women to be aware of their rights and health status to seek appropriate medical services. It is important to study the overall situation and know the differences between rural and urban Vietnamese women to focus on reproductive health issues. The results can be used as an important guide to assist policymakers and managers in evaluating and designing programs and strategies to improve reproductive health services, particularly for ethnic minority women.

Modern media such as TV, radio, newspaper ... has played an important role in raising understanding of reproductive health for women. Owning modern and equal medical facilities is a very important issue of a healthy society. As a result, mass media such as radio and television can raise awareness of issues affecting daily life, family planning programs, poverty alleviation programs, gender issues, human rights issues, etc. Therefore, the focus of this study is to understand the level of understanding of the reproductive health of ethnic minority women and girls in Viet Nam.

2. Theoretical basis

According to Decision 3781/QĐ-BYT 2020 of the Ministry of Health (2021), Reproductive health is a state of complete physical, mental and social comfort that is not merely free of diseases or illnesses related to the reproductive system. Reproductive health thus implies that people can have a satisfying and safe sex life; they are fertile and make their own decisions about when to reproduce. This also implies that everyone including men and women have satisfying and safe sex lives, they are fertile and free to decide when to give birth and the distance between births. Have the right to receive information and access health care services, safe, effective and acceptable family planning measures of their choice, as well as the ability to choose appropriate, non-unlawful abortion methods to ensure that women undergo safe pregnancy and childbirth, give couples the best chance to have a healthy child (Ministry of Health, 2008). According to the research of Dr. Dao Nguyen Dieu Trang (2021), there are 6 reproductive health issues to pay attention to:

(1) Premarital sex is common in many regions of the world and is on the rise. Studies in Asia and Africa show that women and girls are under enormous social and peer pressure to have sex before marriage. The average age of marriage has increased in many countries, so the time at risk of premarital sex is increasing. Many social factors lead to increasing premarital sex, such as access to the media, immigration, the growing hierarchy of rich and poor in society, etc. Having children outside of marriage is a mental and material burden on young mothers. They risk having to raise their children alone without the support of their families and men.

(2) Early marriage and inbreeding:

Early marriage, also known as child marriage, is defined as when one or two people marry before the age of 18 (Holley Catherine, 2011). In Vietnam, early marriage is defined as getting married when one party or both parties are under the age of marriage as prescribed by law, which has been stipulated in the Law on Marriage and Family 2014. This Law also stipulates that the conditions for marriage are: Men from full 20 years old or older, women from full 18 years old and above. Getting married early is against the law. Marriage will not be recognized by law. The pre-legal rights of spouses will not be taken into account (National Assembly, 2014). Early marriage deprives education and employment opportunities, reduces population quality, and maternal and child health. This will adversely affect the reproductive health of the female, since the genital apparatus is not yet complete.

Inbreeding is a marriage between a man and a woman in the same close relative for no more than 3 generations. According to the provisions of the Law on Marriage and Family, people within the three generations are: First generation- parents; second generation- half-siblings, half-siblings, half-parents; third generation, siblings, uncles and uncles, children and aunts (Congress, 2014). According to the results of the 2015 survey, the average inbreeding rate was 6.5%, but it is worth noting that in some ethnic groups the rate is very high. Inbreeding can have many consequences including high infant mortality rates and the risk of population downsizing and is also one of the causes of reduced life expectancy of ethnic groups and is associated with poverty in some ethnic groups.

(3) Pregnancy and childbirth: Comprehensive health care for women before and after childbirth is an important decision in helping to prevent and minimize the risk of harm to the mother's health, reducing the incidence of birth defects in newborns. Teenage pregnancy and childbirth have adverse health effects, including pregnancy-related risks, complications from unsafe abortions and maternal deaths, as well as adverse educational harms and economic consequences.

(4) Abortion: Abortion is a method of using a procedure or medication with the aim of terminating a pregnancy at an early stage of the pregnancy cycle. Abortion, when performed in developed countries under legal regulations when it is legal, is often one of the safest procedures in health (WHO, 2011). However, unsafe abortions (those performed by people without proper training or outside a medical facility) result in approximately 70,000 maternal deaths and 5 million disability cases annually worldwide. Of the 42 million abortions performed annually in the world, 20 million of them are performed unsafely (Culwell KR et al., 2010). Accidents caused by abortion can be infections, injuries during abortion such as perforation of the uterus, hemorrhage. Long-term complications can be the risk of ectopic pregnancy, chronic genital tract infections and infertility (WHO, 2011).

(5) Contraceptives: Contraception, also known as birth control and birth control, is a method or device used to prevent pregnancy. The most effective methods of contraception are sterilization by vasectomy in men and tubal ligation in women, IUDs and implantable birth control (WHO, 2011). This is followed by several hormone-based methods including oral medications, patches, vaginal rings, and injections (WHO, 2011). Less effective methods include physical barriers such as condoms, diaphragms and birth control sponges and fertility awareness methods. Some of the contraceptives used relatively commonly in Vietnam are oral contraceptives, injections, implants, and IUDs. By extending the time between pregnancies, birth control can improve adult women's birth outcomes and the survival of their children (Ahmed et al., 2012).

(6) Inflammatory diseases of the genital tract, sexually transmitted diseases and HIV/AIDS: The likelihood of sexually transmitted diseases of ethnic minority women and girls is higher than normal due to poor sanitation, poverty, and low access to health services, increasing the risk of sexually transmitted diseases. People with a sexually transmitted disease are more likely to develop HIV/AIDS than normal.

3. General situation of reproductive health of ethnic minority women and girls in Viet Nam

3.1. General knowledge of reproductive health

In recent years, the proportion of women and girls in ethnic minority areas with general knowledge of reproductive health has been improving. This is explained by the effective implementation of the Party and state policy, children and women have greater access to knowledge about reproductive health care. According to statistics from the Ethnic Minority Committee and the General Statistics Office in 2019, the proportion of children attending school at the right age accounts for 8.6% for lower secondary school and 47.0% for high school. In most schools, issues of gender, marriage and diseases related to the genital tract are taught by teachers. However, the development of adequate knowledge and the implementation of teaching as a complete subject are still limited. Communication through radio, women's unions and youth unions also showed positive signs. Knowledge of puberty, safe sex and sexually transmitted diseases is gradually gaining popularity. According to statistics from the Ministry of Health, the rate of modern contraceptive use in ethnic minority areas accounts for 56.5%. Adequate knowledge of HIV among adolescents aged 15-19 years also improved at 29%.

3.2. Reproductive health status

In recent years, obstetric mortality has decreased significantly. The maternal mortality rate has fallen from 165 per 100,000 in 2002 to 65 per 100,000 live births in 2018. However, according to 2018 statistics, the maternal mortality rate among ethnic minorities such as Thai, Tay, Bana, Dao, H'mong is four times higher than that of Kinh ethnic groups. This is a huge limitation in the lack of access to the local reproductive health care system. At the same time, child marriage and inbreeding are also responsible for this increase.

The situation of lower genital tract infections among women and girls in ethnic minority areas is at a very high level and is an alarming problem. According to a study by Dao Nguyen Dieu Trang and colleagues (2019), in A Mesh district, Thua Thien Hue province, the rate of inflammation of the lower genital tract reached 2.2%. Accordingly, only 61.5% of girls know how to clean the genital area and more than 42% of children do not know how to prevent inflammation of the lower genital tract.

3.3. Current situation of access to reproductive health care services

In fact, increasing the access to reproductive health care of ethnic minority women and children is a major challenge. In the H'rê, Mong, Cham, Bana people... The practice of home birth is a long-standing tradition. Instead of going to medical facilities, they believed that the ritual before and after childbirth would help the woman and child to be healthy, protected by the gods. Barriers to knowledge and archaic notions make them distrustful of services in health facilities. In addition, geographical distance, language barriers and inability to pay make it difficult for ethnic minority women to access health centers. However, the rate of births in health facilities has tended to increase in recent years. Specifically, according to statistics of the General Statistics Office in 2019, the rate of childbirth at health facilities increased by 22.8% compared to 2015. The average distance of ethnic minority households to the nearest health facility is 14.7 km, down 12% compared to 2015 (16.7 km). The proportion of females aged 10-49 using contraception has improved quite significantly, but the gap compared to the general rate is still very large (nearly 15%). At the same time, the proportion of women visiting antenatal examinations also increased significantly, only 2.7% lower than the general rate. At the same time, although health workers in ethnic minority areas are well-trained, their practical applicability is weak. Therefore, the efficiency of care services is not high.

4. Research Methodology

The participants in this study were ethnic minority women and children aged 15-39 years old who were married or living as husband and wife in ethnic minority communities in Vietnam. The two main data collection strategies used in this study were: focus group discussion (FGD) and in-depth interview (IDI). Focus group discussion (FGD) refers to a qualitative data collection method in which between 6 and 10 subjects are gathered together to discuss a specific topic of interest to the researcher. This approach aims to capture the local context of sexual and regenerative health of ethnic minority women and girls and help investigators get a true picture of social reality. Meanwhile, Deep Interviews uses a semi-structured approach to reach individuals who are in the reproductive health care phase.

Initial surveys in selected communes before conducting TCT research to find out information on demographics, living standards, culture, customs, mobility, marriage age, general cultural level, language, concepts used in the set of questions are understood, the concept of timelines, are people ready for interviews? What is the situation of using pregnancy care services, birth care (before, during and after birth), family planning measures? Also consider who are the investigators that the people trust and will speak most honestly. The data was recorded using Nvivo software, collated with manuscripts, and 215 pages of A4 data were obtained. All the votes received from the field were checked by the data processing team before entering them into the computer.

Our study was conducted in mountainous and remote areas with a total of 852 ethnic minority women between 2017 and 2021. In terms of age, the majority are aged 15-29, accounting for 58.6%, followed by the 29-39 age group, accounting for 34.5%. This is appropriate because the majority of mothers with young children of childbearing age are usually under 30 years old. In terms of education level, the proportion of mothers with secondary education qualifications was the highest, accounting for 32.4%, followed by primary education with 28.3%. In particular, the illiterate of mothers is not small, accounting for 21.7%.

Table 1. Demographics of the subjects studied

Characteristic		Amount	Proportion
People	<i>Muong</i>	349	41,0%
	<i>Hmong</i>	110	12,9%
	<i>Knife</i>	71	8,3%
	<i>Tay</i>	82	9,6%
	<i>Different</i>	240	28,2%
Sum		852	100%
Age range	15 - 19	44	5,2%
	20 - 24	475	55,7%
	25 - 29	133	15,6%
	30 - 34	157	18,4%
	35 - 39	43	5,1%
Sum		852	100%
Education	<i>High school</i>	149	17,5%
	<i>Middle school</i>	311	36,5%
	<i>Primary education</i>	233	27,3%
	<i>Illiteracy</i>	159	18,7%
Sum		852	100%
Number pregnancies of	0	55	6,5%
	1 - 2	509	59,8%
	> 3	287	33,7%
Sum		852	100%

Source: survey research

5. Research results

5.1. Knowledge of reproductive health care

The results showed that the percentage of ethnic minority women who had heard of reproductive health services and options was quite high. Specifically, maternal and child health care, childbirth and family planning reached 87.2%, respectively; 89% and 75%. However, the level of understanding of reproductive health care varies. Most adolescents have little or no understanding of reproductive health services and options. However, some adolescents were able to identify abstinence, the use of condoms and other contraceptives to prevent unwanted pregnancies.

"Reproductive health care is how we protect ourselves to avoid pregnancy, through the use of condoms during sex." (a 17-year-old juvenile of Muong ethnicity).

"At our age we have to choose between having sex until we get married, or if we can't wait any longer, we have to use contraceptives that can prevent us from getting pregnant."

5.2. Accessibility of reproductive health information

On the means of helping ethnic minority women to access information related to reproductive health care: the percentage of people who know from health workers is the highest, reaching 84.9%, respectively. Next, from local officials – women, farmers, youth unions (28.4%) and communal radio reached 37%. In addition, there are many different media sources: friends (15%), movies, play (21.5%), radio/radio (14.1%)

Table 2. Means of providing information on reproductive health

Source	Proportion
Family	5,80%
Friends	15%
Local officials	28,40%
Paramedics	84,90%
Teachers	6%
Radio stations	37%
Radio/radio	14,10%
Movies/photos/plays	21,50%
Books and newspapers	13,80%

Source: survey research

"Most of us get information and ways to take care of ourselves from health care workers and friends" – (29-year-old woman is taking care of 2 young children).

"Most of us get information from schools. Sometimes, parents also provide some information in the form of warnings. I think most of the reproductive knowledge I gained came from discussing it with friends." (19 years old, ethnic Dao).

While the channels for providing information on reproductive health are diverse, there are still cases where there are barriers to access. The four main issues preventing ethnic minority women and children from accessing information are: social culture, lack of privacy on the part of service providers, attitudes of service providers and, finally, perceived adverse effects. In particular, the issue of access is very difficult for young people, especially minors. In general, the community believes that sexual and reproductive health issues are only for adults, so it is easy to have negative reviews when a minor, especially girls, seeks information or has reproductive or sexual problems.

"Some nurses are not polite, especially to us young people. When they go there with a relationship problem, they will yell at you or even insult you saying that you are a bad girl. Some even claim that we went there just to address abortion." (Ethnic Thai, 15 years old).

5.3. Views on premarital sex and contraception

The average age of first sexual intercourse of the subjects was 17.5 years, About 22% of individuals said they had had sex before marriage. Considering this group of people, there are an average of 2 sexual partners and the majority of sex subjects are men of adult age.

This result shows that the rate of premarital relations is not too high. The reason that individuals are afraid is fear of getting pregnant and fear of becoming infected.

"If I have sex before I get married, it will affect my health and I will get HIV and if I have sex first, I will get pregnant, and I don't want to have children anytime soon." (31-year-old woman, ethnic Thai).

"Don't have sex before marriage because it's not good for you, can't go to school and make your family nervous. If you have a previous relationship and that person is not your husband if you are not married." (26-year-old Muong ethnic woman).

"Premarital sex can lead to the possibility of pregnancy. And if they get themselves pregnant, they won't accept to be their husbands and their families will be told that they're wrong about customs." (19 years old of Muong ethnic group).

However, there are still some views that premarital sex is quite common in ethnic minority communities. The majority (about 60%) are aware that this is risky, but the rest of the individuals simply see it as a way of expressing love and keeping a relationship with their partner.

"For us girls, it usually happens to adult men. It's the person who takes care of him, so if he doesn't agree, he risks losing him. When my lover said that if he refused, he threatened not to take care of me anymore and went to marry another girl. So I agreed " (26-year-old woman, Tay ethnicity).

The study also explored condom use during premarital sex because the use of contraceptives for married women was deemed inappropriate (J.M. Kyilleh et al., 2018). About 85% of people who have performed premarital sex reveal that they do not use protective measures. Condoms are said to inhibit pleasure during sex so should not be used. Most of the reasons and decisions not to use condoms come from men. The few remaining women decided not to use it because they didn't want to. Among those who use protection, the rate of use of birth control pills is quite high, about 60%.

"Men often don't want to use contraception because they think it could cause infertility in the future. Men have long-term thoughts about the future life between two people and wish to have children later. So if the girl who uses birth control pills is at risk of infertility in the future, it means that the man has invested in vain." (35-year-old American woman).

Some people claim that it is difficult to buy condoms. This is because minors or unmarried women who buy condoms will be considered "bad girls". In addition, the identities of individuals and their families are easily identified in ethnic minority communities and they do not want their information to be disclosed to their families.

"Condoms are sold in drug stores so it's hard to go there and buy them, especially for us girls, who were teenagers back then. Some people say, I'm too young to buy condoms ." (Hmong woman, 25 years old).

5.4. Unwanted pregnancy, abortion and sexually transmitted infections

Interview results suggest that unplanned pregnancies are a common phenomenon in families in the region (85%). Many individuals in ethnic minority communities believe that pregnancy itself is a guarantee or proof of a woman's fertility. Men will also test their male bravery by increasing the frequency of sex and waiting for news of their wife's pregnancy. Sometimes women may accept unprotected sex in the hope of getting pregnant as bait for marriage as well as future fertility tests.

The abortion rate was only 1.9 percent of the 852 participants. Most subjects are aware that abortion can affect the mother's health and need to use safety measures. "Abortion is affecting the health of the mother because many people do not have the opportunity to have children anymore if they have an abortion" (27-year-old Hmong woman). "In my opinion, if you miss it, you have to raise it because you dare to do it, you have to accept it" (Muong woman, 39, opposes abortion).

However, the percentage of abortions in unwanted pregnancies (56 cases) accounted for 78.8%. And unplanned pregnancies that are aborted by unsafe methods account for a fairly high percentage (about 30%). Most cases use a combination of methods such as drinking boiled bodhi leaf water, nescafe, grinding root, alcoholic beverages and using herbs.

"A friend of mine got pregnant and decided to have an abortion using herbal leaves placed in her vagina. Some also use fruit, lime leaves, nescafe and sugar, alcoholic beverages." (22-year-old Tay woman).

In terms of knowledge on each safe contraceptive method in 852 study subjects: oral contraceptives accounted for 47.6% and condoms 49.2%, ring insertion 24.1%, emergency contraceptives 15.8%, injections 6.3%.

Knowledge of sexually transmitted diseases: The best known sexually transmitted disease is HIV/AIDS (55.9%). *"Having sex with many people can be contagious with many diseases such as HIV/AIDS"* (a 19-year-old Dao woman). The proportion of women and girls from ethnic minorities in the Northwest region in the syphilis and gonorrhoea study were: 48.5%, 31.8%, respectively. The percentage of people who are knowledgeable about fungal infections and flagellates accounts for only 24%. Of the 852 women and girls interviewed, 78.1% of individuals did not report signs of contracting a sexually transmitted disease, 58.3% did not know how to prevent it, and 18.2% did not know what to do when they were infected.

5.5. Knowledge of family planning

The results of family planning guidance activities showed that the majority of married women were instructed in Family Planning (accounting for 83.3%). Of the 710 women and children instructed, the instructors were mainly village health workers and commune health workers (35.6% and 34.0%, respectively). About 20.9% were guided by population officials. The rest are district health officials and other women.

5.6. Knowledge of prenatal and postpartum health care

Table 3. Current status of knowledge on handling dangerous signs during pregnancy

Understanding of handling danger signs	Proportion
To get rid of yourself	6%
Self-healing	3,90%
Invite the midwife to the house	25,60%
Go to the clinic	71,30%
Private clinics	7%
Healer/Garden Lady	6,50%
Worship	4,30%

Source: survey research

In terms of handling dangerous signs during pregnancy, up to 71.3% went to the clinic for medical treatment, followed by inviting midwives to the house (25.6%), 7% to a private clinic. There is still a certain percentage of ethnic minority women and girls to self-medicate, self-medicate or resort to a healer/garden or worship ritual.

Among pregnant women, only 50.2% of mothers had 3 prenatal examinations, 12.9% of mothers did not go to antenatal examinations. In terms of tetanus vaccination, 75.6% of mothers are fully vaccinated; more than 14% do not go for vaccination. In terms of antenatal examination locations of mothers in the same order of proportion as above, the most chosen location is the health station (73.5%), followed by the midwife (29.2%), still about 2% of people call the healer or garden nurse for antenatal examination.

Regarding the choice of place to give birth, although the majorities (about 65%) of those who decide to give birth at a health station or call a private service, nearly 28% of pregnant women do not go to a health facility to give birth but give birth at home or in the forest, shelter, 2.1% fell. This is mainly because of difficult travel conditions, due to habits, due to remote medical facilities, due to lack of money.

6. Solutions to improve reproductive health understanding for ethnic minority women and girls in Viet Nam

According to the research results, the understanding of reproductive health of ethnic minority women and girls is still incomplete. At the same time, many individuals are not aware of the importance of exploring and understanding more about reproductive health. In addition, difficult economic conditions lead to the consequence that people do not take care of enough meals and clothes. Therefore, they do not have the conditions to take care of their own health. In addition, reproductive health care is a delicate issue, they can hardly share, revealing their private issues.

6.1. Solution

Based on the research results and the current situation, in order to achieve the best effect, the author builds solutions in three aspects: self, family and community.

Firstly, strengthen communication, improve knowledge and attitudes about the reproductive health of ethnic minority women and girls. In fact, the situation of child marriage and inbreeding is largely dominated by low education and difficult economic conditions. Therefore, it is necessary to actively propagate anytime, anywhere, so that people can easily access, remember and use effectively. At the same time, integrated lectures are said to lack logic and complete information, making it difficult for students to remember and visualize reproductive health care. Therefore, the author proposes to design it into a complete subject. Here, students learn about the genitalia, menstrual cycle, contraception and related infectious diseases. The author also encourages the application of technological advances such as pictures, power points, videos ... help students visualize and understand better. In addition, priority may be given to piloting the teaching of reproductive health in the mother tongue of ethnic minorities. This makes them feel close and removes language barriers in the communication process.

Second, improve reproductive health knowledge for health workers, schools and parents of ethnic minorities. It can be seen that for ethnic minorities, access to the media is still inadequate. Health workers, youth union officials, schools and parents are the ones who have the right awareness and have an important influence. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the training and methodical training for health workers and teachers. Health workers and teachers must have a deep knowledge and understanding of reproductive health. At the same time, courses on communicating with native speakers also need to be implemented. From there, media

collaborators can confidently share and impart knowledge to women and children. For village health workers, priority is given to sending compatriots participating in training to return to long-term service. In addition, the author proposes to invest in infrastructure and services for health facilities to improve the quality and efficiency of reproductive health services.

Third, promote community participation in improving reproductive health for ethnic minority women and girls. For health care to be accepted and popular everywhere, community involvement is required. First, reproductive health services need to meet the criteria of privacy, confidentiality, respectful and non-judgmental attitudes. To do so, it is necessary to arrange a separate fertility counseling room, ensuring that women and girls feel safe and comfortable. Moreover, it is necessary to invest funds in local programs and activities, specifically periodic free reproductive health visits or ensure that contraceptives are provided free or affordable to the economic situation of the people. In order to implement effectively, cadres need to combine with reputable people in villages such as village elders and patriarchs to mobilize people to trust and follow. Since then, the use of contraception has been normalized in the moral conception of ethnic minorities.

Fourth, strengthen the leadership and representation of ethnic minority women in decision-making processes in the community, specifically as women's association presidents. As a result, it is easy to connect women in the village with local officials to propagate, engage and raise public awareness. In addition, it is possible to raise awareness of related areas such as land rights, people, social services... They are the bridge that communicates ideas effectively.

6.2. Recommendations

For commune-level and district-level health facilities

Firstly, health workers at commune and district levels have the spirit of respecting the different cultural characteristics in the behavior and birth habits of ethnic women. At the same time, create conditions for pregnant women and their family members to perform a number of appropriate religious rites if required in conditions to ensure the health of pregnant women and newborns. At the same time, implement a program to support home births.

Secondly, increase the number of female commune and district health workers trained to meet the standards. In the face of religious and belief barriers, female health workers are more easily accepted and trusted by the village. Female health workers are also more favorable in attaching, sharing and advising on reproductive health for pregnant women.

Third, strengthen coordination between health facilities at all levels in implementing training activities, fostering professional knowledge on reproductive health. Training activities should be organized periodically, ensuring the requirements for handling possible cases well. At the same time, note the integration of sensitive elements of cultural values and customs.

Fourth, cooperate with village elders, clan leaders – prestigious people in the village to spread the word about knowledge, attitude and implementation of reproductive health. A specific example is to visit households with pregnant women during the maternity period, organize propaganda sessions with the presence of village elders ... Finally, regularly check the quality of medical equipment, facilities – infrastructure. From there, make timely remediation proposals to superior agencies.

For state management agencies

First, the State shall develop a standard framework to improve the quality of reproductive health of women and girls in ethnic minority areas. This is the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of reproductive health

improvement activities in ethnic minority areas. At the same time, it is data for analysis, quantification and implementation of appropriate measures in localities.

Second, develop policies to protect vulnerable ethnic minorities. Accordingly, ethnic minorities are provided with free health insurance and are instructed to use health insurance properly. Bring the rights of children and women closer to ethnic minorities so that they are aware of the role of reproductive health care and protect themselves.

Third, state budget investment in improving health facilities and infrastructure in remote areas. Create conditions for people to access advanced, modern and appropriate reproductive health care technology.

Fourth, the vicious cycle of poverty, inequality and low intellectual population are deep-rooted problems that lead to many consequences among ethnic minorities, including reproductive health. Therefore, solving the deep-rooted problems of poverty, inequality, and raising people's intellectual level is a radical solution to improve reproductive health for ethnic minority people.

References

- i. Ministry of Health (2008), *Reproductive Health*, Education Publishing House, Hanoi, pp. 30 – 32.
- ii. Ministry of Health, *Decision 3781/QĐ-BYT 2020 on the promulgation of the "national action plan on sexual and reproductive health care for adolescents and young people for the period 2020-2025"*.
- iii. Cao Ngoc Thanh, Nguyen Vu Quoc Huy, Dao Nguyen Dieu Trang, (2017), *Research on knowledge, attitudes and practices on reproductive health care in adolescent girls of ethnic minorities, Thua Thien Hue province*, *Journal of Medicine and Pharmacy, Hue University of Medicine and Pharmacy*, volume 7 (04) 1/2017, pp. 21-28
- iv. *Reproductive health care for ethnic minorities (2022)*. Retrieved 10/19/2022 at <https://suckhoedoisong.vn/cham-soc-suc-khoe-sinh-san-cho-dong-bao-dan-toc-thieu-so-169211128160507626.htm>
- v. *United Nations Agency for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women (2021)*. *Policy summary: gender issues among ethnic minorities in the country*.
- vi. Dao Nguyen Dieu Trang (2021). *Study the current state of biological health and evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention model in adolescent female adolescents in the mountainous district of A Mesh, Thua Thien Hue province, Hue*. Pp 7 – 10.
- vii. Dao Nguyen Dieu Trang, Phan Thi Bich Ngoc, Nguyen Vu Quoc Huy, (2017), *Research on knowledge, attitudes and practices on reproductive health care in adolescent girls in A Mesh district, Thua Thien Hue province*, *Journal of Medicine and Pharmacy, Hue University of Medicine and Pharmacy*, volume 6 (06) in August 2017, pp. 85-89
- viii. *Plan 29/KH-UBND in 2021 on Reproductive health care, sexual health for adolescents and young people in the period of 2021-2025 in Hoa Binh province. (2022)*. Retrieved 2022-10-19 at <https://hethongphapluat.com/ke-hoach-29-kh-ubnd-nam-2021-ve-cham-soc-suc-khoe-sinh-san-suc-khoe-tinh-duc-cho-vi-thanh-nien-thanh-nien-giai-doan-2021-2025-tren-dia-ban-tinh-hoa-binh.html>
- ix. *Some findings about ethnic minority women through the UNWomen report (2022)*. Retrieved 10/19/2022 at <https://hoilhpn.org.vn/tin-chi-tiet/-/chi-tiet/mot-so-phat-hien-ve-phu-nu-dan-toc-thieu-so-qua-bao-cau-cua-unwomen-40649-6601.html>
- x. World Bank and National Institute of Nutrition, 2019. *Report "Persistent Malnutrition in Ethnic Minority Communities in Viet Nam: Problems and Interventions": Of the 3 ethnic minority children, 1 was stunted; and out of 5 children, 1 is underweight*.

- xi. Ngo Thi Van Phong, 2019. (Department of Ethnic Education, Ministry of Education and Training). *Child marriage and inbreeding in ethnic minority areas.*
- xii. *Make efforts to ensure that ethnic minority students attend school at the right age.* (2022). Retrieved 2022-10-19 at [http://ubdt.gov.vn/tin-tuc/tin-tuc-su-kien/y-te-giao-duc/no-luc-dam-bao-hoc-sinh-dtts-di-hoc-dung-do-tuoi.htm#:~:text=Theo%20k%E1%BA%BFt%](http://ubdt.gov.vn/tin-tuc/tin-tuc-su-kien/y-te-giao-duc/no-luc-dam-bao-hoc-sinh-dtts-di-hoc-dung-do-tuoi.htm#:~:text=Theo%20k%E1%BA%BFt%20)
- xiii. National Assembly (2014), *Marriage and Family Law.*
- xiv. General Statistics Office (2014) ,*Survey assessing the targets of children and women.* Retrieved 10/19/2022 at <https://www.unicef.org/vietnam/vi/ch%E1%BB%A7-%C4%91%E1%BB%81/b%C3%A1o-c%C3%A1o-%C4%91%E1%BB%81u-tra-%C4%91%C3%A1nh-gi%C3%A1-c%C3%A1c-m%E1%BB%A5c-ti%C3%AAu-tr%E1%BA%BB-em-v%C3%A0-ph%E1%BB%A5-n%E1%BB%AF>
- xv. General Statistics Office of Vietnam (2019), *Preliminary results of the Population and Housing Census 2019.* Retrieved 10/19/2022 at <https://www.gso.gov.vn/default.%20aspx?tabid=382&idmid=2&ItemID=19277>
- xvi. Vietnam Committee for Ethnic Minorities (2015), *Results of the survey on the economic and social situation of 53 ethnic minorities in 2015, accessed on 18/10/2021, at the website http://ubdt.gov.vn.* P26
- xvii. Ahmed, S.; Li, Q.; Liu, L.; Tsui, A.O. (2012). "Maternal deaths averted by contraceptive use: An analysis of 172 countries". *The Lancet.* 380 (9837): 111–25. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60478-4. PMID 22784531. Archived from the original on 2013-05-10.
- xviii. Culwell KR, Vekemans M, de Silva U, Hurwitz M (2010). "Critical gaps in universal access to reproductive health: Contraception and prevention of unsafe abortion". *International Journal of Gynecology & Obstetrics.* 110: S13–16. doi:10.1016/j.ijgo.2010.04.003. PMID 20451196.
- xix. Holley Catherine (2011), *Helpdesk Report: The impact of girls' education on early marriage.*
- xx. World Health Organization Department of Reproductive Health and Research (2011). *Family planning: A global handbook for providers: Evidence-based guidance developed through worldwide collaboration (PDF).* Geneva: WHO and Center for Communication Programs. ISBN 978-0-9788563-7-3.